

MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES USED IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORKS

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Abstract:

Wireless sensor network (WSN) refers to a group of spatially dispersed and dedicated sensors for monitoring and recording the physical conditions of the environment and organizing the collected data at a central location. Clustering is applied to divide the network into clusters and each cluster is having a cluster head in which we perform data collection. In many cases, while we are collecting different types of data there is chance of redundancy in the data while forming a cluster and thus the size of the data packets are increased. There is a need to aggregate the data at the cluster head such that data can be compressed into less number of packets and redundancy is also

decreased. The Clustering Techniques used are “Affinity Propagation” and “Spectral Clustering” and finally a comparison under various performance metrics like delay , CPU usage, execution time are done between the algorithms under the data aggregation protocol is done and the efficient algorithm of the two is concluded. The most efficient algorithm of the two is considered as the one used to reduce redundancy in Wireless Sensor Networks(WSN)

Introduction

A Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is a wireless network consisting of spatially distributed autonomous devices using sensors to cooperatively monitor physical or environmental conditions at different locations, such

as temperature, sound, and vibration. The nodes which sense, which have the capability of sensing the physical phenomena that occur around them. The sensor nodes have one of the components as a sensor and these sensor nodes collectively they form a network which is called the wireless sensor network. Wireless Sensor Networks is gaining popularity and gaining importance like Area monitoring, Health Care monitoring, Air pollution monitoring, Industrial monitoring e .t. c. The communication architecture of Wireless Sensor Networks is shown as below:

Fig1: WSN Communication Architecture

The application of advanced machine learning techniques in WSN has been increased widely. Machine learning algorithms are very flexible to apply for many WSN applications. Machine Learning algorithms are often categorized as supervised, unsupervised and reinforcement. Labeled dataset is provided with

supervised learning algorithm. In case of unsupervised learning, labeled data is not provided with the algorithm. By finding the similarities between the input samples, it classifies the samples into different groups (clusters). In reinforcement learning algorithm, the agent learns by means of communicating with its surroundings. Data aggregation is the process of gathering data and presenting it in a summarized format. An efficient data aggregation is imperative at the cluster head (CH) to reduce the redundancy and send meaningful data to the BS.

The paper is sequenced as follows: The second section contains the types of Machine learning algorithms that are used in WSN. The third section provides information about the need of using ML algorithms in WSN. Section 4 provides information about various clustering algorithms that are used to transfer data from one sensor node to other sensor node in Wireless Sensor Networks. Section 5 provides the proposed solution for the usage of Clustering algorithms. Performance analysis of the algorithms used will be provided in Section6 along with the best suggested algorithm. The paper is concluded in Section 7.

II. Machine Learning in Wireless Sensor Networks

A. Supervised Learning

In this type of Machine Learning the machines are trained using a labeled training data. Basically the main aim of supervised learning algorithm is to find the mapping function to map the input variable to output variable. Supervised Learning can be clearly understood by the below example diagram:

Fig2: Supervised Learning

Regression and Classification algorithms are used to get the required output. Supervised learning algorithms are extensively used to solve several challenges in WSNs such as localization and objects targeting, Security and intrusion detection.

B. Unsupervised Learning

In Unsupervised Machine Learning the models are not given a labeled dataset instead the model itself finds out the hidden patterns and insights from the given data. It is more often compared to human brain in learning things. The goal of unsupervised machine learning algorithm is to find the underlying structure of a dataset, group the data according to similarities and represent the data in a compressed format.

Fig3: Unsupervised Learning

Here, an unlabeled data is given and it will interpret the raw data to find the hidden patterns from the data and then will apply suitable algorithms such as different clustering algorithms and Decision trees etc. Unsupervised learning is used for more complex tasks as compared to supervised learning because, in unsupervised

learning, we don't have labeled input data. Unsupervised Machine Learning is considered to be more advantageous for Wireless Sensor Networks.

C. Reinforcement Learning

It is a Machine Learning technique in which the agent learns automatically using feedbacks without any labeled data. RL solves a specific type of problem where decision making is sequential, and the goal is long-term, such as game-playing, robotics e.t.c.

Fig3: Reinforcement Learning

Agent is an entity that can perceive. Environment is a situation in which an agent is present or surrounded with. Actions are the moves taken by an agent within the environment. Reward is the feedback returned to the agent from the environment. In RL, the agent is not instructed about the environment and what actions

need to be taken. It is based on the hit and trial process. The agent takes the next action and changes states according to the feedback of the previous action. The agent may get a delayed reward. The environment is stochastic, and the agent needs to explore it to reach to get the maximum positive rewards. Thus for Reinforcement ML technique it takes more delay to produce the results by default as it is more of a hit and trail process. Among the elements of Reinforcement Learning, Policy is a way in which an agent behaves at a given time. The most well known Reinforcement Learning technique is Q-Learning technique.

Fig4: Visualization of Q-learning method

$$Q(st+1, at+1) = Q(st, at) + \gamma(r(st, at) - Q(st, at))$$

where $r(st, at)$ denotes the immediate reward of performing an action at a given state st , and γ is the learning rate that determines how fast learning occurs. This learning method is generally used and implemented in distributed architectures like WSNs.

III. Usage of ML algorithms in WSN

Sensor networks usually monitor dynamic environments that can actually change rapidly over time and it is utmost important to adapt and operate efficiently in such environments. ML algorithm is used to identify and remove the nonfunctional nodes from routing schemes and compress data at Cluster Head in case of Clustering. Wireless Sensor Networks monitor dynamic environments that change rapidly over time. This dynamic behavior is either caused by external factors or initiated by the system designer themselves. To adapt to such conditions, sensor networks often adopt machine learning techniques to eliminate the need for unnecessary redesign. It also prolongs the lifespan of the network. WSNs are usually deployed in complicated environments where researchers cannot build accurate models to describe the system behavior. Most of the WSNs need complex algorithms to solve them while very few can be prescribed using simple mathematical models. ML generally provides low complexity estimates for a system model. More importantly security enhancements of WSNs are drastically changed using Machine Learning techniques. Some of the important earnings of using ML in Wireless Sensor Networks are a follows:

- a. It saves the sensor nodes energy and significantly expand WSN lifetime by preventing the misleading data.
- b. Enhances network reliability by eliminating faulty and malicious data.
- c. Sensor network designers often use large amounts of data but sometimes unable to extract important correlations in the sensor data e.g., in node connectivity and energy sustainability. ML methods can then be used to discover important correlations in the sensor data.
- d. Incase of real time applications like volcano eruption and waste water monitoring. ML techniques are used to calibrate a WSN to new knowledge about the environment.
- e. ML is often used in intelligent decision making and autonomous controlling.
- f. ML makes computing processes more efficient, reliable and cost-effective. ML produce models by analyzing even more complex data automatically, quickly and more accurately.

IV. Overview of the Clustering algorithms used in WSN

A.K-Means Clustering

It is an iterative algorithm that divides the unlabeled dataset into k different clusters in such a way that each dataset belongs to only one group that has similar properties. The two main tasks carried on by K-Means is to determine the best value for “ K ” center points in an iterative process and assign each data point to its closest k -center. The algorithm is as follows:

Select the number K to decide the number of clusters. Select random K points or centroids. Assign each data point to their closest centroid, which will form the predefined K clusters. Calculate the variance and place a new centroid of each cluster. Repeat the third steps, which means reassign each datapoint to the new closest centroid of each cluster. If any reassignment occurs, then again calculate variance and place new centroid of each cluster. There are number of ways to find the number of clusters K . K-means follows Expectation-Maximization approach to solve the problem. The Expectation-step is used for assigning the data points to the closest cluster and the Maximization-step is used for computing the centroid of each cluster. The below figure shows a K means clustering graph.

Fig5: Visualization of K-means clustering

The figure shows the formation of three clusters and here the value of k is 3. As K-means clustering is an iterative process it gives its best after the number of iteration increases.

B. DBSCAN

DBSCAN is mainly based on the distance between nearest points. In general first we calculate similarities and then we use it to cluster the data points into groups or batches. The focus here is on Density-based spatial clustering of applications with noise (DBSCAN). The major importance for DBSCAN is we need not specify the number of clusters. All that we need is a function to calculate the distance between values and some guidance for what amount of distance is considered “close”. DBSCAN also produces more reasonable results as compared to K-means. It can discover clusters of different shapes and sizes

from a large amount of data, which is containing noise and outliers. The basic parameters used in DBSCAN are minimum number of points clustered together in a region and ϵ (ϵ) which will be used to locate points in neighborhood of any point. The algorithmic steps in DBSCAN algorithm are:

- The algorithm proceeds by arbitrarily picking up a point in the dataset (until all points have been visited).
- If there are at least 'minPoint' points within a radius of ' ϵ ' to the point then we consider all these points to be part of the same cluster.
- The clusters are then expanded by recursively repeating the neighborhood calculation for each neighboring point

Fig6: Visualization of clusters formed by DBSCAN

The above graph shows the formation of clusters in DBSCAN algorithm.

C. Agglomerative Clustering

It is also known as *AGNES* (*Agglomerative Nesting*). The algorithm starts by treating each

object as a singleton cluster. Next, pairs of clusters are successively merged until all clusters have been merged into one big cluster containing all objects. The result is a tree-based representation of the objects, named *dendrogram*. Agglomerative clustering works in a “bottom-up” manner. That is, each object is initially considered as a single-element cluster (leaf). At each step of the algorithm, the two clusters that are the most similar are combined into a new bigger cluster (nodes). This procedure is iterated until all points are member of just one single big cluster (root). The following steps are used :

1. Preparing the data
 2. Computing (dis)similarity information between every pair of objects in the data set.
 3. Using linkage function to group objects into hierarchical cluster tree, based on the distance information generated at step 1. Objects/clusters that are in close proximity are linked together using the linkage function.
 4. Determining where to cut the hierarchical tree into clusters. This creates a partition of the data.
- This way the a dendrogram is formed as a result.

Fig7: Visualization of Agglomerative Clustering

The above figure describes the Agglomerative Clustering that is the hierarchical division of complex entities. It is mainly good for identifying small clusters.

The algorithms that are illustrated above are some of the clustering algorithms used in Wireless Sensor Networks under various conditions. In general the specified algorithms take more time in execution or in memory usage. The below section contains the algorithms which are used in our project.

V. Algorithms Used in Proposed Solution and their Performance Analysis

A. Affinity Propagation

In Affinity Propagation, each data point sends messages to all other points informing its targets of each target's relative attractiveness to the

sender. Each target then responds to all senders with a reply informing each sender of its availability to associate with the sender, given the attractiveness of the messages that it has received from all other senders. Senders reply to the targets with messages informing each target of the target's revised relative attractiveness to the sender, given the availability messages it has received from all targets. The message-passing procedure proceeds until a consensus is reached. Once the sender is associated with one of its targets, that target becomes the point's exemplar. All points with the same exemplar are placed in the same cluster. It is also a graphic technique for sorting items according to its similarity. It is used in unifying large amounts of data. For each node i and each candidate exemplar k , AP computes the "responsibility" $r(i, k)$, which indicates how well suited k is as an exemplar for i , and the "availability" $a(i, k)$ reflecting the evidence that i should choose k as an exemplar.

$$r(i, k) \leftarrow s(i, k) - \max_{k' : k' \neq k} \{a(i, k') + s(i, k')\}$$

$$a(i, k) \leftarrow \min \left\{ 0, r(k, k) + \sum_{i' : i' \neq i, k} \max \{0, r(i', k)\} \right\}$$

Where the matrix $s(i, k)$ denotes the similarity (eg. edge weight) between the two nodes i and k , and the diagonal of this matrix contains the preferences for each node. The above two equations are iterated until a good

set of exemplars emerges. Each node i can then be assigned to the exemplar k which maximizes the sum $a(i, k) + r(i, k)$, and if $i = k$, then i is an exemplar. A damping factor between 0 and 1 is used to control for numerical oscillations.

Fig8: Visualization of Clusters formed in Affinity Propagation

The above figure shows the formation of clusters in Affinity Propagation after every iteration.

The process of Affinity Propagation is as follows:

1. Let X_1 through X_n be a set of data points and S be the function that quantifies the similarity between any points, such that $s(i, k) = -\|x_i - x_k\|^2$ (similarity matrix)

2. The responsibility matrix R has values $r(i, k)$ that quantify how well-suited X_k is to serve as an exemplar for X_i .

3. The availability matrix A contains $a(i, k)$ that represents how "appropriate" it would be for X_i to pick X_k as its exemplar.

4. Iterations are performed until the cluster boundaries remain unchanged over a number of iterations. Finally those exemplars are extracted. (criterion matrix)

The highest criterion value of each row is designated as the exemplar. Rows that share the same exemplar are in the same cluster. It is most commonly used for computational tasks. The below figure is the representation of a graph that is plotted with Affinity Propagation Algorithm

Fig9: Visualization of Affinity Propagation graph

The parameters that are considered for performance analysis and their values for Affinity Propagation are:

Execution Time: 1.168s

CPU Usage : 2.5 clock seconds

Memory Usage : 6.4 %

Disk Usage: 35.8%

B. Spectral Clustering

Spectral clustering is an exploratory data analysis technique that reduces complex multidimensional datasets into clusters of similar data in fewer dimensions. The goal is to cluster the full spectrum of unorganized data points into several groups based upon their similarity. Spectral Clustering groups similar data, regardless of features, around common points. This technique with roots in graph theory, where the approach is used to identify communities of nodes in a graph based on the edges connecting them. The method is flexible and allows us to cluster non graph data as well. It is used for metric modification such that it gives a much more global notion of similarity between data points as compared to other clustering methods. It thus represents data in such a way that it is easier to find meaningful clusters in new representations. It is especially used in complex datasets where traditional clustering methods would fail to find the groupings. Spectral clustering uses information from the eigen values (spectrum) of special matrices built from the graph or the data set. We'll learn how to construct these matrices, interpret their spectrum, and use the eigenvectors to assign our data to clusters. Spectral clustering is a flexible approach for finding clusters when your data doesn't meet the

requirements of other common algorithms. It treats each data point as a graph-node and thus transforms the clustering problem into a graph-partitioning problem. The implementation of spectral clustering algorithm is done in three steps:

1. A similarity matrix is built in the form of an adjacency matrix which is represented by A . The adjacency matrix that is built in this step is built in two manners i.e; using Epsilon neighborhood graph and using K nearest neighbors or a fully connected graph.
2. Projecting the data into a low dimensional space. This step is generally done to account for the possibility that members of the same cluster may be far away in the given dimensional space. Thus the dimensional space is reduced so that those points are closer in the reduced dimensional space and thus can be clustered together by a traditional clustering algorithm. It is done by computing the Graph Laplacian Matrix . To compute it though first, the degree of a node needs to be defined. The degree of the i th node is given by

$$d_i = \sum_{j=1}^n |(i,j) \in E| w_{ij}$$

The Degree Matrix is defined as follows:

$$D_{ij} = \begin{cases} d_i, & i = j \\ 0, & i \neq j \end{cases}$$

where i, j are the nodes of the graph and w_{ij} is the weight between the nodes i and j . And after this step the Graph Laplacian Matrix is defined as:

$$L=D-A$$

Where D is the Degree Matrix and A is an Adjacency Matrix. First, the eigenvalues and the respective eigenvectors are calculated. If the number of clusters is k then the first k eigenvalues and their eigenvectors are taken and stacked into a matrix such that the eigenvectors are the columns.

3. First, each node is assigned a row of the normalized of the Graph Laplacian Matrix. Then this data is clustered using any clustering technique. To transform the clustering result, the node identifier is retained.

The main idea of using Spectral Clustering method is the method is flexible and it also allows us to cluster non graph data as well. The below

figure shows the visual of a spectral clustering graph.

The figure depicts three clusters formed through spectral clustering technique. One remarkable advantage of spectral clustering is its ability to cluster “points” which are not necessarily vectors, and to use for this a “similarity”, which is less restrictive than a distance.

The parameters that are considered for performance analysis and their values for Spectral Clustering are:

Execution Time: 27.122s

CPU Usage : 6.5 clock seconds

Memory Usage : 67.9 %

Disk Usage: 35.8%

VI. Comparison Of performance of Algorithms:

MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS USED	EXECUTION TIME	CPU USAGE (%)	MEMORY USED (%)	DELAY	DISK USAGE (%)
SPECTRAL CLUSTERING	27.122s	6.5	67.9	High	35.8
AFFINITY PROPAGATION	1.168s	2.5	6.4	Low	35.8

Based on the above performance Analysis table of the two algorithms Affinity Propagation and Spectral Clustering , the best algorithm that is most suitable for Wireless Sensor Networks is Affinity Propagation. Here a comparison is considered between the algorithms that are specified above and in terms of all the parameters considered Affinity Propagation is considered as the best algorithm.

VII. Conclusion

The aim of the project is to suggest a best algorithm for Clustering in Wireless Sensor Networks. For this

purpose two of the widely known and modern day clustering algorithms are considered i.e; Spectral Clustering and Affinity Propagation. Spectral Clustering an exploratory data analysis technique that reduces complex multidimensional datasets into clusters of similar data in fewer dimensions. It has its roots in graph theory. Affinity propagation is a clustering algorithm that is based on the concept of “message passing” between data points. Based on different parameters like Execution time, CPU usage, Memory Used percent, Disk Usage percent and comparing the Delay in both the algorithms Affinity Propagation is considered to be the most efficient algorithm for Wireless Sensor Networks.

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